

Road to Nowhere? Evaluating the Impact of Transport Infrastructure on Local Economic Development in Greater Tzaneen Municipality, Limpopo, South Africa

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Transport infrastructure is a fundamental catalyst for local economic development, as it directly impacts business operations, investor attraction, and the general quality of life in communities. In South Africa, as stipulated by the Constitution and supported by the National Land Transport Act, are entrusted to develop, implement, and manage legislation and policies related to land transport within the jurisdictions of the respective municipalities. However, the legacy of apartheid and post-apartheid financial mismanagement has left significant gaps in infrastructure, particularly in the Greater Tzaneen Municipality (GTM). These challenges are compounded by corruption, insufficient funding, and a lack of skilled personnel, despite various national efforts to address the deficit, including Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs). As the paper argues, while the government's role in financing transport infrastructure is undisputed, local municipalities must find innovative ways to bridge the gap. The South African experience offers valuable lessons, particularly from the City of Johannesburg, whose well-maintained and integrated transport systems serve as a model for smaller municipalities. However, 'there is no denying the elephant in the room' transport issues in many areas, especially rural ones, are simply not roadworthy for economic growth. As emphasized by the Development Bank of South Africa (DBSA), "well-developed infrastructure reduces production and consumption costs", a notion that GTM must embrace, if it ever hopes to grow beyond its pothole-riddled roads. Through improved planning, investment, and collaboration, GTM can begin to tackle its transport infrastructure issues head-on. 'A stitch in time saves nine', or in the case of transport infrastructure, one investment might save a whole lot of time, money, and frustration. The findings of this study indicate a strong correlation between transport infrastructure and local economic development (LED), suggesting that investment in transport infrastructure plays a crucial role in fostering local economic growth. A qualitative-research approach was employed in this study to gather in-depth information on the phenomenon under study.

Keywords: Transport infrastructure, local economic development, greater tzaneen municipality

"Where there is no road, there is no journey," an African proverb that highlights the importance of transport infrastructure as the backbone of local economic development, much like a well-constructed road that leads to prosperity. Transport infrastructure is a critical driver of local economic development, playing a crucial role in promoting business opportunities, attracting investors, and enhancing the quality of life for communities (Diene, 2024). Given its importance, it is essential for local municipalities to prioritize the development and maintenance of transport infrastructure. This is further emphasized by Section 153 of the 1996 Constitution of South Africa, which outlines the developmental responsibilities of municipalities as a fundamental mandate. Section 11 of the National Land Transport Act 5 of 2005 supports the development of Local government by outlining the municipal responsibility to ensure that transport needs are accomplished within their jurisdiction (NLTA 5,

2005). Furthermore, Section 40 of the Constitution promotes cooperative governance, as affirmed in the White Paper on Local Government (1998) and Section 3 of the Municipal Systems Act (Municipal System Act 32 of 2000). These provisions suggest that the developmental responsibilities outlined in Section 153 of the Constitution can be effectively achieved through collaborative efforts.

The White Paper on National Transport Policy 1996 aims to provide safe, reliable, effective, efficient, and fully integrated transport operations and infrastructure (White Paper on National Transport Policy, 1996) As strengthened by the 1994 Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP) emphasized community-based development, aligning closely with the effective governance of transport infrastructure (RDP, 1994). However, the legacy of apartheid left significant gaps in the country's transport infrastructure. This issue was further exacerbated by poor financial management in the post-apartheid era, where corruption prevailed in the allocation of transport development projects in municipalities. Scholars have long highlighted the - importance of transport infrastructure for economic growth (Banerjee, Duflo, & Qian, 2020; Tong & Zhang, 2024) stressing the need for urgent attention to address these infrastructure deficits. As outlined in the White Paper on National Transport Policy 1996, efficient transport networks are essential for the smooth flow of goods and services, which in turn

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supports economic development (White paper on National Transport Policy, 1996).

The Development Bank of South Africa (DBSA, 1998); along with researchers such as Jouanjean, Gachassin, and Velde (2022); and Wan et al. (2022) have emphasized the positive link between infrastructure and growth. They argue that well-developed infrastructure reduces production and consumption costs, thus facilitating economic transactions. For example, better roads make transportation faster and more efficient, reducing fuel and time costs for businesses make it easier for goods and services to be exchanged in the economy, thereby promoting economic activity and growth. Conversely, inadequate transport infrastructure can have detrimental effects on living standards and hinder economic development (Sénquiz-Díaz, 2021). Although the GTM has made strides in improving transport infrastructure, further investments are needed to create a competitive market environment and attract investment.

Transport infrastructure is often considered a public good, with governments playing a central role in funding and ensuring equitable access. However, the funding of road infrastructure in GTM remains a complex and contentious issue. While some scholars argue that funding challenges persist (Van Rensburg & Krygsman, 2019) the National Treasury has countered that sufficient financial resources are available for transport infrastructure development, as evidenced by the 2024 Budget Speech (National Treasury, 2024). According to BusinessTech (2022), and the National Treasury (2024), the government allocated over R812 billion to public sector infrastructure over three years, with more than a third of this amount earmarked for transport and logistics, including funding for the South African National Roads Agency (SANRAL) to improve the road network (News 24, 2023).

Effective transport networks are essential for unlocking economic potential, improving living standards, and fostering integrated development (Schachtebeck & Mbuya, 2006; Khumalo, 2013; Umoh & Effiong, 2024). Road infrastructure development is central to addressing economic deprivation and promoting sustainable growth. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) have emerged as a promising model for financing road construction and maintenance (Esperilla-Niño-de-Guzmán et al., 2024). Given the challenges in narrowing the financing gap, governments have increasingly focused on leveraging PPPs to ensure the delivery of infrastructure projects critical for service provision in developing countries (Mofokeng, Alhassan, & Zeka, 2024). The recent amendments to National Treasury Regulation 16 and Municipal Regulation 309 highlight the government's commitment to improving the governance and effectiveness of PPPs. By incorporating feedback from both the public and private sectors, these regulations are designed to address real-world challenges, enhance transparency, and foster better cooperation among stakeholders (National Treasury, 2024). Improved road infrastructure not only stimulates economic growth but also facilitates production, consumption, and external connections. As noted by Pucher et al. (2007) and Cho and Choi (2021) investments in transport infrastructure reduce accidents, mitigate environmental impacts, and enhance both residents' welfare and economic growth. However, challenges related to road infrastructure remain significant barriers to economic and social progress in GTM, thus imperative for the study of transport infrastructure in the context of local economic development to be undertaken.

Problem Statement

Despite increased infrastructure expenditure in South Africa, the

2006 South African Institution of Civil Engineers (SAICE) report highlighted insufficient investment in infrastructure maintenance, with much of the infrastructure in poor condition (Mazele & Amoah, 2022). This issue is particularly evident in the Greater Tzaneen Municipality (GTM), where deteriorating transport infrastructure particularly roads directly hamper local economic development and exacerbates poverty. While South African policy frameworks emphasize the developmental role of municipalities in transport infrastructure, the legacy of apartheid and poor financial management as highlighted by (Vivek, 2024) have left significant gaps in infrastructure development. These gaps are compounded by corruption and challenges in securing sufficient funding. Although some progress has been made, further investment is necessary to improve competitiveness, attract investment, and facilitate economic activity. Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) have been identified as a potential solution to address funding gaps (Chiswa, 2024; Ramolobe & Khandanisa, 2024) however, the implementation in GTM remains underdeveloped.

Review of Literature

Transport Governance and Legislative Framework in South Africa

The governance and legislative framework in South Africa's transport sector is fundamental to ensuring the efficient operation of transport systems that support both the economic and social needs of the country. The Department of Transport is the key governmental body responsible for regulating and overseeing transport policies, legislation, and the establishment of transport entities. It plays a crucial role in creating safe, effective, and sustainable transport infrastructure, which is vital for economic growth and social development. The government also works to attract investment by creating an enabling environment through supportive policies (DBSA, 1998; Dhlamini, 2024). An efficient and well-developed transport infrastructure can enhance both domestic and foreign investments, driving economic growth and improving connectivity. Several pieces of legislation govern the transport sector in South Africa, which ensures a structured approach to managing and developing transportation systems. This paper focuses on three major legislative acts and policies that guide transport governance: the National Land Transport Act (NLTA) 5 of 2009, the White Paper on National Transport Policy of 1996, and the National Transport Master Plan (NTMP).

National Land Transport Act (NLTA) 5 of 2009

The National Land Transport Act (NLTA) 5 of 2009 is the primary legal framework that regulates land transportation across South Africa. Its aim is to facilitate the transformation and restructuring of the national land transport system to meet the demands of a growing economy and population. The NLTA provides clear guidelines for municipal authorities, such as the Greater Tzaneen Municipality, to consider when developing road infrastructure and urban transport planning. Section 11 of the Act outlines the responsibilities of municipalities in addressing local transport needs, emphasizing the importance of meeting socio-economic demands. Section 12 encourages intergovernmental cooperation in addressing transportation issues across different levels of government. Chapter 4 of the Act stresses the importance of partnerships with various stakeholders, including environmental and urban planning

authorities, to ensure the sustainable development of transportation systems and mitigate negative environmental impacts. Municipalities are also encouraged to collaborate with other transport authorities to gain expertise and improve the efficiency of their transport systems (NLTA 5, 2009).

White Paper on National Transport Policy (1996)

The White Paper on National Transport Policy, released in 1996, establishes the vision and strategic direction for South Africa's transport sector. This policy positions transportation as a key enabler for socio-economic development, recognizing its importance in facilitating growth, job creation, and access to essential services. The White Paper sets out the country's goals for safe, reliable, efficient, and integrated transport systems. It also emphasizes the need for sustainable transport operations that balance environmental considerations with economic and social objectives. The policy outlines clear objectives for improving the safety, accessibility, and affordability of transport, particularly for underserved communities. It calls for the development of a multi-modal transport network that can provide seamless integration across different modes of transport, including road, rail, and public transit, to support South Africa's development (White Paper on National Transport Policy, 1996).

National Transport Master Plan (NTMP)

The National Transport Master Plan (NTMP) is a long-term strategic framework that aims to prioritize the modernization and upgrading of South Africa's transportation infrastructure. The NTMP outlines a vision for the development of a sustainable, dynamic, and integrated transport system that can meet the needs of the population and the economy. For municipalities like Greater Tzaneen, the NTMP provides critical insights into improving transport infrastructure and services. However, the municipality faces significant challenges, including outdated transport stations, unsafe buses, and deteriorating road conditions. These issues highlight the importance of aligning local development plans with the NTMP's objectives of creating a multi-modal, long-term transportation system that enhances mobility and supports economic growth. The NTMP envisions a 2050 framework for transportation systems that incorporates modern technologies, efficient networks, and enhanced service delivery strategies to improve the quality of transport services across South Africa (NTMP, 2050). Despite the challenges faced at the local sphere, the NTMP represents a key document that shapes the future trajectory of transportation in the country.

Transport Infrastructure Challenges and Impact on Local Economic Development in Greater Tzaneen Municipality

The Greater Tzaneen Municipality faces several pressing challenges related to its transport infrastructure, which has hindered both economic growth and social well-being. One of the most significant issues is the poor condition of roads, which has been directly linked to losses in business profitability, tourism, and investment opportunities (Jonsson, 2004; Sebola, 2014; Duranton, 2015; Guo & Li, 2024). The municipality's failure to improve public transport and road infrastructure has exacerbated these economic losses and disproportionately affected vulnerable populations, particularly people with disabilities (Tyler, 2017; Kang, 2023). The limited availability of public transport options, which predominantly rely on mini-bus taxis and buses, restricts mobility and travel choices for

residents. Rural communities within the municipality face even greater challenges, as they often have limited access to safe roads (Madyibi, 2022). In these areas, residents are forced to travel long distances to access basic transport facilities, which infringes on their basic human rights, as guaranteed in the Constitution of South Africa 1996. Despite the existence of national rural transport strategies aimed at improving access to transport in rural areas (NLTTA, 22 of 2000) the municipality has struggled to effectively implement these plans. Several factors contribute to this failure, including financial constraints, a shortage of skilled personnel, and land tenure, which have made it difficult to develop and maintain the required infrastructure (Mamokhere, 2024; Zindi & Majam, 2024; Pillay & Kikasu, 2024; Bester, 2024). The deteriorating state of transport infrastructure has had serious social and economic consequences, including outmigration, as residents seek better opportunities in areas with more reliable infrastructure. The quality of road infrastructure directly impacts people's daily lives (Tini, Zaly, & Sultan, 2018; Pandey & Pathak, 2025) as poor road conditions create significant financial burdens and safety risks (Snieska & Simkunita, 2009). This is especially evident in the municipality's agricultural sector, where inadequate transport infrastructure limits trade, restricts access to markets, and hampers economic opportunities (Hove-Sibanda, Awino, & Agyemang, 2025; Chibaro, Mahwine, Cynthia, Morima, & Boy, 2025). Poor road conditions not only disrupt the movement of goods but also hinder the efficient delivery of essential services, such as healthcare and education, which are crucial for improving the living standards of residents.

Improving transport infrastructure, particularly roads in GTM requires significant investment in skilled personnel, resources, and the development of a robust, sustainable transport planning framework. This includes addressing the need for capacity building and fostering collaboration between local authorities, national government agencies, and private sector partners. Transport planning must also prioritize inclusivity and community engagement, ensuring that all residents, particularly those in rural areas, have equitable access to transportation options (Allen & Farber, 2020). The impact of transport infrastructure on local economic development is undeniable. Transport networks are essential for facilitating the movement of goods and services, which is fundamental to economic productivity and growth. Well-developed infrastructure not only provides access to essential services like schools and hospitals but also enhances mobility, which directly increases productivity and supports economic development (Nafziger, 2012). Improved transport infrastructure can enhance access to markets, reduce the cost of goods, and increase income levels, benefiting both businesses and consumers (Gannon & Liu, 1997).

Investment in road infrastructure can also attract private sector investment and stimulate various sectors, including tourism, regional development, and foreign trade (Bayes, 2014; Smith, 1998). The absence of adequate transport infrastructure limits the growth potential of the municipality, as it discourages investment and economic activity (Thobela, 2024). Furthermore, infrastructure development can improve living standards by creating jobs, facilitating trade, and promoting economic cooperation both within the region and internationally (Challoumis, 2024). Therefore, investing in and improving transport infrastructure not only addresses immediate needs but also drives long-term economic benefits by enhancing stronger, more interconnected communities,

promoting sustainable growth, and ensuring that development is inclusive of all sectors of society.

The Linkage between Road Infrastructure Investment (Public-Private Partnerships) and Local Economic Development

Transport infrastructure plays a vital role in driving economic development (Weisbrod, 1997; Diene, 2024). The South African government has long recognized its importance, implementing several initiatives aimed at improving infrastructure, such as the Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP, 1994); the Growth, Employment, and Redistribution strategy (GEAR, 1996); and the Accelerated Shared Growth Initiative for South Africa (ASGISA) (Mlambo-Ngcuka, 2006). These initiatives highlight the government's commitment to enhancing transport systems to support broader economic objectives. In recent years, there has been a notable increase in investment towards road infrastructure development, with significant budget allocations for maintaining and improving roads, railways, and public transport systems. The South African National Roads Agency Limited (SANRAL) plays a central role in managing and upgrading the national road network, facilitating trade, mobility, and connectivity across the country (SANRAL, 2025). The 2021/2022 national budget reflected substantial investments in the transport sector, with an average annual expenditure growth rate of 81%, from R57.3 billion in the 2020/2021 fiscal year to R72.5 billion in 2023/24 (National Treasury, 2023). Although a significant portion of the budget is directed towards railway infrastructure, considerable funds are allocated to SANRAL for road infrastructure, including provincial and city-level transport services. Former Minister of Transport Fikile Mbalula, during his 2021 budget speech, emphasized the government's intent to remain within fiscal ceilings for employee compensation while addressing transport sector challenges. The budget aimed to address urgent needs such as relief funds for the taxi industry during the pandemic and providing personal protective equipment (PPE) for transport workers (Department of Transport, 2021).

Efficient public transport networks are crucial for economic centres to function optimally. Recognizing this, the Department of Transport has introduced funding mechanisms, such as the Public Transport Grant, which supports the development of integrated transport networks in cities. This funding has increased at an average annual rate of 15.7%, from R4.4 billion in 2020/2021 to R6.8 billion in 2023/2024, addressing the challenges the industry faces (National Treasury, 2023). The Department also allocated R104.1 billion for the maintenance and development of national and provincial road networks in 2021. SANRAL manages most of these funds, focusing on upgrading and rehabilitating national roads. Provincial road maintenance subsidies amount to R37.5 billion to cover resealing, rehabilitation, and patching of roads (Department of Transport, 2023). However, road infrastructure investments are not without environmental implications. Transport is a major contributor to air pollution and emissions in large cities, negatively impacting human health and the environment (D'Angioli, 2019). In response, the South African government, in collaboration with environmental departments, is working on introducing electric vehicles and autonomous technologies to reduce emissions and improve transport sustainability (Moeletsi, 2021; Mphahlele, 2023). Investment in road infrastructure is essential for local economic development, facilitating the efficient movement of goods and people, which is

crucial for trade, industrial production, and services. High-quality rural roads are particularly vital for transporting raw materials to factories and finished goods to markets, directly supporting business operations and economic activities (Adler & Polsky, 2010; Haghshenas & Vaziri, 2012; Prud'homme, 2005).

Road infrastructure also plays a critical role in logistics and trade, especially in rural areas where road networks often represent the only means of accessing economic opportunities. Developing road infrastructure involves significant initial costs and long-term management requirements. Governments have traditionally partnered with the private sector to manage and fund these projects but increasing fiscal constraints have raised concerns about the efficiency of public sector involvement. As a result, public-private partnerships (PPPs) have gained prominence, leveraging private sector investment and expertise for more cost-effective infrastructure development (Oliver, 2015). According to the Department of Transport (2025), South Africa's road network spans approximately 535,000 kilometres, with additional reports suggesting a total of 750,000 kilometres. The South African National Roads Agency Limited (SANRAL) manages a significant portion, generating revenue through tolls, fuel levies, and other charges to maintain and modernize the network (SANRAL, 2025). Despite generating substantial funds, South Africa faces fiscal challenges, complicating the funding of infrastructure projects. Key revenue sources for road infrastructure funding in South Africa include the fuel levy, tolls, and vehicle-related charges, with funds allocated by the National Treasury as highlighted by (VanRensburg & Krygsman, 2019). The "user pays" principle is generally applied, but there is limited clarity on its implementation and on how much users should contribute. Local municipalities also apply this principle in various ways, such as through parking fees, to support road infrastructure financing. Private sector involvement is crucial for road infrastructure development, particularly in agricultural-based municipalities like GTM. Businesses are encouraged to collaborate with the government, contributing to road maintenance and development, which improves accessibility, and mobility, and attracts international investment. This collaboration enhances the financial viability of large infrastructure projects, making them more attractive to investors and benefiting the local economy

Lessons from the City of Johannesburg, A Metropolitan Perspective

The City of Johannesburg, widely recognized as the economic hub of South Africa, has emerged as one of the country's fastest-growing economies (Business Tech, 2019; Rogerson, Malovha, & Rogerson, 2024). This metropolitan city has developed competitive and well-maintained road infrastructure that is often cited as among the best in Africa. With a rapidly expanding economy and a dynamic urban environment, Johannesburg has made significant strides in improving transportation systems (Thobela, 2024; Ngcobo, Akinradewo, & Mokoena, 2024) facilitating both economic growth and social inclusivity. Johannesburg's transport infrastructure is characterized by a variety of effective and integrated transportation modes that serve both the inner city and surrounding townships (Risimati, 2021; Risimati, Gumbo, & Chakwizira, 2021). One of the city's most successful initiatives is the implementation of the Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) system according to (Matshika, 2023; Harber, 2023) which has been extended to the townships and informal settlements, providing affordable and reliable transportation to

previously underserved areas. The BRT system, which operates on dedicated bus lanes, has alleviated traffic congestion and improved the overall mobility of residents in the city, making public transport more accessible and efficient. The research by Risimati (2021) alluded that the Gautrain, a rapid rail network, continues to serve as an essential transportation option by reducing traffic congestion within the city and connecting Johannesburg with other key urban centres like Pretoria and the OR Tambo International Airport. Public transport in townships, such as Alexandra, has also improved significantly, with affordable and reliable services catering to the needs of residents. This development has helped bridge the transport gap in these areas, offering a sustainable solution to mobility challenges and improving the overall quality of life for township residents.

The Gauteng Provincial Government has also made substantial investments in transport infrastructure, underscoring its commitment to enhancing the city's transport network. In 2020, the Gauteng MEC for Transport announced a budget allocation of over R7.7 billion for transport development programs, aimed at further improving public transportation systems and upgrading road infrastructure across the province (Gauteng Department of Roads & Transport, 2019). This funding is expected to bolster ongoing efforts to enhance connectivity and accessibility, particularly in high-density areas such as townships and informal settlements. Moreover, the Johannesburg Road Agency (JRA), an entity under the Gauteng Department of Transport, plays a pivotal role in the city's road management and development. The JRA is tasked with ensuring the provision of safe, accessible, and liveable roads, along with the planning, design, construction, and rehabilitation of infrastructure, including bridges and traffic signals (Daily Maveric, 2018). Through this agency, Johannesburg has made significant progress in maintaining its road networks, contributing to the city's economic growth, and ensuring safe mobility for its residents. The JRA's efforts to modernize and maintain transport infrastructure demonstrate the critical importance of local governance in driving urban development and fostering economic opportunities through effective transport systems (JRA, 2025).

In the 2025/26 financial year, the Gauteng Department of Roads and Transport was allocated R9.7 billion, with R28 billion projected over the Medium-Term Expenditure Framework (MTEF), primarily for providing a safe, reliable, and affordable integrated transport system (Timeslive, 2025). These investments and the JRA's dedicated efforts are crucial for enhancing connectivity, accessibility, and mobility within Johannesburg, thereby supporting the city's economic growth and improving the quality of life for its residents. These investments reflect a strong commitment by the City of Johannesburg to enhance its transport infrastructure, underscoring the city's focus on improving mobility, connectivity, and overall economic growth. The substantial funding and efforts put into transport development highlight the importance of strategic planning and collaboration between local governments and key stakeholders. For municipalities like Greater Tzaneen (GTM), it is crucial to benchmark these successful initiatives to understand how they can replicate such efforts in their Municipality. This is particularly important for the establishment of an entity capable of addressing the municipality's transport mandate. By learning from Johannesburg's approach-integrating targeted investments, effective resource allocation, and enhancing partnerships, GTM can improve its transport infrastructure and contribute to its broader economic

and social development goals.

Method

This study adopted a qualitative research methodology to explore the role of transport infrastructure in the local economic development of the Greater Tzaneen Municipality (GTM), focusing on identifying key challenges and proposing potential solutions. Chalmers and Cowdell (2021) Understand qualitative methodology as a type of research that focuses on exploring and understanding people's experiences, perspectives, behaviors, and social phenomena through non-numerical data. The qualitative approach facilitated an in-depth exploration of the socio-economic impacts of transport infrastructure, incorporating both the subjective experiences of residents and key stakeholders in GTM, alongside broader national and global trends in transport governance. The research employed a descriptive and exploratory design to investigate the various dimensions of transport infrastructure and its implications for economic development, aiming to gather insights from diverse sources to understand the complex interplay between infrastructure, governance, funding, and community needs within GTM. Data was primarily collected through document analysis, which involved an extensive review of relevant government reports, policies, and academic literature on transport infrastructure in South Africa. Morgan (2022) strongly observes data analysis as the systematic process of reviewing and interpreting documents to gather relevant information for a study. This included analyzing key legislative frameworks such as the National Land Transport Act (2009) the White Paper on National Transport Policy (1996) and the National Transport Master Plan (NTMP), all of which provide the context for transport governance in South Africa.

Discussion

The study reveals a strong relationship between transport infrastructure and local economic development, a connection that is readily observable. In the case of Greater Tzaneen Municipality (GTM), inadequate transport infrastructure presents a significant constraint on local economic development, particularly in key sectors such as agriculture, trade, and tourism, all of which are vital to the local economy. Poor road conditions lead to increased transportation costs, delays, safety risks, and restricted access to markets, hindering business operations and access to essential services like healthcare and education. This, in turn, exacerbates poverty and inequality in the area. The deteriorating infrastructure has contributed to migration from rural areas within the municipality to places with better infrastructure, further intensifying social and economic challenges. The municipality's struggles in implementing national rural transport strategies are compounded by financial constraints, a shortage of skilled personnel, and land tenure issues, all of which limit its capacity to develop and maintain infrastructure. The study also highlights the crucial role of government policies and legislative frameworks such as the National Land Transport Act (NLTA) 5 of 2009, the White Paper on National Transport Policy (1996), and the National Transport Master Plan (NTMP), which provide a roadmap for safe, efficient, and integrated transport systems. However, the implementation of these policies at the local level, especially in GTM, has been inconsistent. While these frameworks are well-intentioned, the municipality faces challenges in securing sufficient funding and expertise to meet its ambitious goals. Moreover, ineffective collaboration with other spheres of

government and stakeholders has hindered the full realization of these frameworks.

Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) are identified as a potential solution to address the funding gaps and inefficiencies in infrastructure development. By leveraging private sector investment and expertise, PPPs could improve road construction and maintenance in GTM. However, the research highlights the underdevelopment of PPPs in the municipality due to governance challenges and limited implementation capacity. The study recommends that GTM adopt more robust and transparent PPP frameworks to attract private sector investment, reduce the burden on public finances, and improve service delivery. Improving road infrastructure is crucial for boosting local economic productivity. Better road conditions reduce transportation costs, lower the cost of goods and services, and facilitate trade, which benefits both producers and consumers. Improved infrastructure also stimulates sectors like agriculture and tourism, creates job opportunities, and attracts investment. The study suggests that significant investments in road infrastructure could unlock GTM's economic potential, improve living standards, and drive long-term economic growth. Drawing lessons from the city of Johannesburg's successful development of competitive and well-maintained road infrastructure, the study suggests that GTM could benefit from developing an integrated transport system that includes both urban and rural areas. Johannesburg's Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) system, which integrates different transportation modes to meet the needs of a growing urban population, serves as a model for GTM to promote mobility and economic activity across the municipality. Furthermore, Johannesburg's ability to attract investment through effective governance and collaboration between public and private sectors can serve as a benchmark for GTM. Despite significant funds allocated to national infrastructure development, financing road infrastructure in GTM remains a challenge due to fiscal constraints and budgetary pressures. While the National Treasury has allocated substantial funding for infrastructure, the municipality struggles to secure adequate local funding. The study stresses the need for better financial management, the effective utilization of these funds in the local sphere, and the adoption of innovative funding models like PPPs to bridge the financing gap and ensure sustainable infrastructure development.

Conclusion

Transport infrastructure is crucial for the local economic development of the Greater Tzaneen Municipality (GTM), facilitating business opportunities, enhancing the quality of life, and attracting investment. However, despite legislative frameworks like the National Land Transport Act, the White Paper on National Transport Policy, and the National Transport Master Plan, GTM faces significant challenges, including poor road conditions, unreliable public transport, and inadequate funding. These issues hinder economic activities, exacerbate poverty, and disproportionately affect vulnerable populations, particularly in rural areas. The findings highlight the urgent need for substantial investment in road infrastructure to unlock the municipality's economic potential. While the South African government has made strides in improving infrastructure funding, financial constraints, corruption, and a shortage of skilled personnel continue to hamper effective implementation. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) present a promising solution to these challenges, though their application in

GTM remains underdeveloped. Recommendations include prioritizing infrastructure maintenance and upgrades, building local government capacity, fostering collaboration between the public and private sectors, and ensuring inclusive transport planning that guarantees equitable access for all residents, especially those in rural areas. Future research could examine the long-term impact of improved road infrastructure on economic indicators such as income levels, employment, and investment, as well as the effectiveness of PPPs and the environmental implications of sustainable transport technologies like electric vehicles.

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